

THE COVID-19 SCENARIO AND NURSING CARE IN THE URGENT AND EMERGENCY SETTING

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Introduction: At the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, when information about the pathogen and its control measures was scarce, a new working condition was imposed on health professionals, making it necessary to address the impacts on the work of nurses and nursing staff, who were at the forefront of caring for patients with SARS-CoV-2 infection. **Objective:** To describe the impact and repercussions of the COVID-19 pandemic on the work of nurses and staff in urgent and emergency care units. **Methodology:** This is a literature review carried out from March to May 2023, consulting the databases Virtual Health Library of the Ministry of Health, LILACS, BDNF and Google Scholar, using descriptors contained in the Health Sciences Descriptors (DeCS): "Pandemic"; "Nursing professionals"; and "Working conditions". To develop the review, 10 scientific studies in Portuguese were selected through exploratory reading, using inclusion and exclusion criteria. The criteria used to select the studies were: articles published in the national literature whose main theme was the study of the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on professional nursing care, between the years 2019 to 2023. **Results:** In addition to significant changes regarding the need for adequate structure and organization of the flow of care, with considerable overcrowding and increased demand in urgent and emergency services, it was observed that the COVID-19 pandemic has also brought several stressors to nursing professionals working on the front line. It was evident that fear related to exposure to the virus and insecurity were the most pertinent feelings, enhanced by the lack of adequate materials for personal protection and the lack of training for the team to properly manage patients with signs and symptoms of Sars-Cov-2 infection, as well as those who were infected but asymptomatic. In addition to this, there was the isolation and fear of infecting family members, as well as the exhausting working hours already experienced. **Conclusion:** Considering all the impacts caused by the COVID-19 pandemic, it is clear that it is important to establish protocols that ensure psychological support and ongoing education for nurses and staff, seeking to qualify and articulate strategies for dealing with vulnerabilities, specifically for those working in urgent and emergency services.

Keywords: Pandemic. Nursing professionals. Working conditions.

Thematic area: Urgent and emergency care in the face of Covid-19.